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Rampal Coal-Fired Power Station: Evaluating its Impacts on the Biodiversity and Ecosystem Resilience of the Sundarbans

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REVIEW PAPER

Rampal Coal-Fired Power Station: Evaluating Its Impacts on the Biodiversity and Ecosystem Resilience of the Sundarbans

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Abstract

The Rampal Power Station (RPS), a 1,320-megawatt coal-fired power plant in Bangladesh, has generated substantial controversy due to its proximity to the Sundarbans, the world's largest mangrove forest and a UNESCO World Heritage and a Ramsar site. The plant, a joint venture between Bangladesh and India, was initiated to address regional energy needs. Environmental concerns associated with the RPS could include forest fragmentation, air and water pollution, habitat destruction, and threats to biodiversity. The plant's coal combustion process would release harmful pollutants, and coal transportation and waste disposal could likely introduce additional pollutants that might affect soil, water, air quality, and human health. Together these factors could potentially disrupt the Sundarbans' delicate ecosystem. Socio-economic impacts are also significant, with potential reductions in resources vital for local communities, including fishing and agriculture, and health risks from increased pollution. The broader implications include potential climate change effects, such as altered weather patterns and increased salinity intrusion. The paper suggests implementing advanced pollution control technologies, strict environmental regulation enforcement, and a shift towards renewable energy sources to mitigate these impacts. Restoring and expanding mangrove forests is also recommended to counterbalance some ecological damage. The RPS represents a complex challenge where the benefits of increased energy production must be carefully weighed against the substantial ecological and socio-economic costs.

Keywords: Sundarbans, coal-fired powerplant, mangrove forest, ecological significance, climate change

Note: In this article, the term "Sundarbans" is used in singular and plural forms. The plural form ("Sundarbans") refers to the forest, while the singular form ("Sundarbans") denotes the region.

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Introduction

The Rampal Power Station (RPS) (Figure 1) is located in Bagerhat, Khulna, Bangladesh (The Independent, 2011). Covering 1,834 acres, this 1,320-megawatt coal-fired plant is the largest in the country (Rahman, 2013). It is situated about 14 kilometers north of the Sundarbans, the world's largest mangrove forest, which is both a UNESCO World Heritage site and a Ramsar site.

Figure 1. (A) Location of Rampal Power Station in Khulna, Bangladesh. (B) A distant view of the power station (Credit: কুপি বাতি, WC, 2022).

In August 2010, Bangladesh Power Development Board (PDB) and India's NTPC signed a Memorandum of Understanding to jointly construct the RPS, with a 50:50 equity split (Manjurul, 2012). The project, with a total cost of around \$1.5 billion, was planned for completion by 2016, funded by a mix of equity and loans (Sengupta, 2016). Named Bangladesh India Friendship Power Company Limited (BIFPCL) (Sengupta, 2016), the company received a 15-year tax exemption status (Ritu, 2013; The Independent, 2013). Bharat Heavy Electricals Ltd (BHEL) was awarded the \$1.68 billion construction contract in July 2016, with a planned operational date of July 2019 (Aitken and BankTrack, 2016). Construction started in January 2018, with the first phase completing in October 2022 and commercial production beginning in December 2022 (Dhaka Tribune, 2022). However, operations faced interruptions due to coal shortages, funding issues, and mechanical failures. As of April 2024, Unit 2 was expected to be operational by March 2024 (Dhaka Tribune, 2023; Sajid, 2023; Songbad Prokash, 2023; BPDB, 2024).

The power plant's proximity to the Sundarbans has sparked major environmental concerns, as its construction and operation threaten the delicate ecosystem of this area. This paper discusses the potential effects of the RPS on the environment and biodiversity of the Sundarbans.

Environmental Concerns Surrounding the RPS

The RPS has faced significant controversy from the public and environmental activists due to its proximity to the Sundarbans. Its 14 kilometers distance from the northern edge of the Sundarbans, breaches the requirement that such projects be situated more than 25 kilometers from the edge of ecologically sensitive areas (Kumar, 2023). UNESCO requested a comprehensive Strategic Environmental Assessment to evaluate the project's cumulative effects due to its location near the

Sundarbans (UNESCO, 2023). Activists argue that the plant's location also violates the Ramsar Convention, an international treaty aimed at conserving wetlands, which Bangladesh is a signatory to. While the plant is intended to meet regional energy needs, its potential environmental impact raises significant concerns.

The Sundarbans is a unique and delicate ecosystem, housing diverse flora (Prain, 1903; Rahman et al., 2015; Siddiqui, 2016) and fauna (Acharja, 2024), including the critically endangered Royal Bengal tiger. It serves as a natural barrier against cyclones and storm surges, safeguarding coastal communities. Because of its proximity to the Sundarbans, the operation of the RPS poses a significant threat to the area's ecological balance.

Critics of the RPS argue that relying on coal for energy is not a smart approach, especially given the global shift towards renewable energy. With its significant potential for solar and wind power, Bangladesh should focus on investing in sustainable and eco-friendly energy sources. Continuing to depend on coal not only risks environmental damage but also obligates the country to a high-carbon future, undermining global efforts to address climate change.

Environmental Impacts

Coal-fired power plants burn coal to produce high-pressure steam. The steam drives a turbine and in turn, the turbine spins a generator to produce electricity. A typical 500 MW plant generates about 125,000 tons of ash and 193,000 tons of sludge annually. These wastes contain toxic metals like mercury, cadmium, and chromium (Islam, 2018), which can contaminate soil, groundwater, and drinking water. These toxic elements have deleterious health effects in humans (Jaishankar et al., 2014).

Burning coal also releases harmful pollutants like sulfur dioxide (SO₂), nitrogen oxides (NO_x), particulate matter, and mercury vapor into the air. These pollutants can negatively impact human health and the environment (EPA, 2024a; ALA, 2023; EPA, 2024b). Acid rain from SO₂ and NO_x emissions can damage mangrove vegetation and aquatic life by disrupting the pH balance of the soils and the water bodies in the Sundarbans, disrupting its fragile ecosystem (Witchalls, 2022).

Impact on Air Quality and Public Health

As stated earlier, burning coal releases large amounts of carbon dioxide, sulfur dioxide, nitrogen oxides, and particulate matter into the atmosphere, significantly contributing to air pollution. The RPS operation is expected to increase air pollution in the region. Emissions of fine particulate matter (PM_{2.5} and PM₁₀) can worsen air quality, leading to respiratory and cardiovascular problems for local people (CARB, 2024). Additionally, sulfur and nitrogen compounds can cause acid rain, which alters the pH of soil and water, impacting plant and aquatic life in the Sundarbans.

Given the Sundarbans' low-lying geography and vulnerability to natural disasters, the added air pollution could further heighten health risks for the area. Accumulation of pollution could also weaken the Sundarbans' ability to cope with climate change. Increased temperatures and rising sea levels, combined with pollution, might impair the mangroves' role as a carbon sink, thus contributing further to climate change.

Coal Transportation and Spillage

It is reported that the plant will need 4.72 million tons of imported coal each year, requiring a lot of large-capacity ships to transport it to the port on the Poshur River. The 40-kilometer route from the port to the power plant goes through the Sundarbans. During transport, uncovered coal can release fly ash, coal dust, sulfur, and other toxic chemicals. Additionally, the release of carbon monoxide and sulfur dioxide could endanger the surrounding areas, leading to the destruction of habitats and a decline in biodiversity of the Sundarbans (GEM Wiki, 2024). The increased river traffic noise would further disturb and threaten the fragile ecosystem. Regular dredging of the Poshur River to maintain navigability could also disrupt the river ecology, harming the aquatic animal populations.

Forest Fragmentation and Habitat Loss

Mangrove ecosystems, such as the Sundarbans, are extremely sensitive to environmental changes, and the construction and operation of the RPS in close proximity pose significant threats to the region. Infrastructure development associated with the plant, including land acquisition, road building, and the installation of transmission lines, will likely result in the fragmentation of the forest. This fragmentation can lead to the loss of critical habitats for a wide range of species. Pollution from the plant, including emissions and wastewater discharge, has the potential to drastically alter soil composition and degrade water quality, further endangering both plant and animal life.

The compounded effects of human activity, habitat loss, and pollution could severely disrupt the delicate balance of this ecosystem, threatening the survival of numerous species, including mammals, reptiles, amphibians, birds, and fish. Endangered species like the Royal Bengal tiger and estuarine crocodiles, which rely on the unobstructed habitats of the Sundarbans for survival, face an especially high risk of decline and perhaps extinction. As biodiversity is lost, the region's ecological health will deteriorate, affecting not only wildlife but also the communities that depend on the Sundarbans for their livelihood. Additionally, the destruction of the mangroves, which serve as carbon sink and natural barriers against storms and tidal surges, would leave the region more vulnerable to natural disasters.

Water Pollution and the Risk to Aquatic Life

The power plant will use 219,600 cubic meters of water daily from the Poshur River for cooling (The Guardian, 2017). This water will be returned to the river as treated wastewater containing various pollutants. The discharge of heated wastewater may also lead to thermal pollution. Raising water temperatures would reduce its oxygen levels, harming aquatic life and disrupting fish habitats (Perch Energy, 2023; Shafak, 2023; The Washington Post, 2017). Additionally, the disposal of coal ash into the river waters poses a significant threat. If not managed properly, coal ash can contaminate water with heavy metals such as arsenic, lead, and mercury (Jaishankar et al., 2014). These toxins can enter the food chain, affecting the wildlife vigor and human health. This contamination could degrade water quality and harm fish populations and other marine species crucial to local livelihoods and the Sundarbans' biodiversity.

Climate Change

The power plant is expected to consume over 4 million tons of coal annually. Burning such a large quantity of coal will release substantial amounts of greenhouse gases into the environment. The emissions from burning coal will gradually contribute to the overall warming of the region. Over time, this will aggravate climate change, leading to more severe long-term consequences. These emissions could intensify extreme weather events, indirectly affecting local areas by disrupting weather patterns, increasing the risk of soil erosion, and worsening salinity intrusion in nearby regions.

Socioeconomic Impact

The Sundarbans, a vital lifeline for millions of people, provide essential resources like fish, timber, firewood, thatching materials, medicinal plants, and honey. However, potential environmental damages caused by the RPS in this region could severely reduce the availability of these resources, threaten local food security, and undermine the livelihoods of those dependent on them. As emissions from the power plant contribute to air and water pollution, nearby communities could experience a rise in respiratory and waterborne diseases, further threatening the regional public health.

While the RPS may aim to support Bangladesh's energy needs and boost the national economy, the long-term environmental and socio-economic consequences could far outweigh these benefits. The degradation of the Sundarbans could lead to the loss of natural storm barriers, making the region more vulnerable to cyclones and rising sea levels. Additionally, the destruction of the Sundarbans' carbon sequestration capacity would aggravate climate change, and the loss of biodiversity and natural beauty could cripple tourism, a key source of income for local communities. Long-term environmental damage could cripple the region's socio-economic fabric, harming both the people and the environment of the Sundarbans. The combined environmental and socio-economic damage may ultimately erode the region's resilience, leaving its people more vulnerable to both natural disasters and economic instability.

Mitigation Measures and Alternatives

To minimize the impact of the Rampal Power Plant on the Sundarbans, several mitigation strategies could be considered:

- Implementing pollution control technologies, such as flue gas desulfurization (a process of removing sulfur compounds from the exhaust emissions of fossil-fueled power stations, which can remove up to 95% of the sulfur dioxide) and selective catalytic reduction (a technology to reduce the emission of nitrogen oxides to near-zero), could reduce emissions from the plant. However, these technologies are costly and may not fully eliminate environmental risks.
- Strict enforcement of environmental regulations and ongoing monitoring of the power plant's impact on the Sundarbans are vital for identifying and mitigating potential damage. Environmental impact assessments should be transparent with the involvement of independent experts and local communities.

- Importing high-quality coal with low sulfur content would also help reduce pollution.
- Shifting to renewable energy sources like solar and wind power could provide a more sustainable solution for Bangladesh's energy needs without threatening the environment. This transition would also support global climate change efforts.
- Reforestation efforts to restore and expand mangrove forests can help mitigate the environmental damage from the power plant. These initiatives would offer increased protection against erosion and boost biodiversity.

Conclusions

The RPS has sparked intense debate due to its proximity to the Sundarbans, the world's most famous mangrove forest – home to a wide range of flora and fauna, including some endangered species. The construction and operation of this power plant poses several environmental challenges, including air and water pollution, habitat loss, threats to biodiversity, and the integrity of the forest. Despite its potential to address Bangladesh's energy needs, maintaining the vitality of this forest cannot be overlooked.

The environmental concerns surrounding the RPS are profound. The coal combustion process introduces harmful pollutants into the atmosphere and water, affecting both the delicate ecological balance of the forest and human health. The risks associated with coal transportation, forest fragmentation, and thermal pollution further complicate these issues. The potential destabilization of local weather patterns and increased salinity intrusion due to greenhouse gas emissions affect the broader climatic consequences.

To mitigate these impacts, several strategies, such as investing in advanced pollution control technologies, enforcing stringent environmental regulations, and transitioning to renewable energy sources like solar and wind power should be pursued. Additionally, restoring and expanding mangrove forests can help counter some of the damage.

The RPS presents a complex challenge where the potential benefits must be carefully weighed against the significant ecological and socio-economic costs. Addressing these concerns through thoughtful and proactive measures will be essential in preserving the Sundarbans' unique and invaluable ecosystem for future generations.

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